

Survey Questions

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Background

During Summer 2019, Metadata 2020 conducted a survey to gain better insights about the familiarity and usage of metadata by several scholarly communications stakeholders. The survey was reviewed by the UAB Office of the IRB.

This document contains the questions that were asked. Respondent answers and analysis of the results can be found in the accompanying paper, <paper name> published in <journal name> <DOI>

Survey Introduction Text

WHAT IS METADATA?

Metadata is “data about data” and is often, but not always, a structured or standardized way to describe a research object. Research objects include, but are not limited to articles, book chapters, books, datasets, images, audio/video recordings, code, or other archival materials.

WHAT WE ARE TRYING TO LEARN

The purpose of this study is to understand the familiarity and usage of metadata by those who use metadata in the process of preparing, publishing, cataloging, or sharing research papers, media and other associated objects in scholarly communications.

ABOUT THIS SURVEY

This survey asks multiple choice and ranking questions, with a few short answer options. We estimate that this will take about

15 minutes to complete. At the end of the survey, you will have the option to provide your contact information (phone and email) to participate in a one-time phone call at a later date where the researcher may ask for clarification or further detail about your responses. This optional call will be scheduled at your convenience and will also take about 15 minutes. You do not need to provide any contact information to participate in the online survey.

Participation is voluntary. The survey is being used for research purposes only and your name and contact information (if you decide to provide it) will not be given to anyone. Your responses will be kept confidential.

WHO IS CONDUCTING THIS SURVEY?

Metadata 2020 is a collaboration that advocates richer, connected, and reusable, open metadata for all research outputs, which will advance scholarly pursuits for the benefit of society. Projects, including this survey and its subsequent analysis, are designed and conducted by volunteer community contributors. Crossref has contributed use of this survey tool.

SUB-SURVEY SELECTOR

1. What is your primary role? *
 - Librarian
 - Publisher
 - Repository Manager
 - Researcher

Librarian Survey

INTRODUCTION

We are interested in what you and your patrons know about metadata; how metadata is generated to describe research objects; how you use metadata in instruction; and how your patrons use metadata to find, assess and use research objects.

What do we mean by “metadata”?

Examples of common metadata for research are bibliographic components, including authors, title, publication date, journal name, volume, pages, subjects, keywords, and digital object identifiers (DOI). This information is often indexed to make articles and other scholarly communication findable in databases and tools such as JSTOR, ProQuest, EBSCO. In your role, you may create this metadata and/or instruct/consult your patrons on metadata use in various platforms.

What do we mean by “your patrons”?

For the purposes of this survey, your patrons may include undergraduate students, graduate students, faculty, professional-level researchers and others who produce scholarly communications.

In thinking about these things, please tell us a bit about yourself and consider the questions below:

TELL US ABOUT YOU

2. What is your library/information science specialty or subject area?

3. Does your instruction/consultation work include teaching research management software?

- Yes
- No

TELL US ABOUT THOSE YOU WORK WITH

4. How does your library support metadata education for patrons/researchers?

5. What is the role of services for and support of metadata in your library?

6. How do you interact with the needs of patrons/researchers in your daily work? (select all that apply)

- Data deposit consultations
- Collection level cataloging
- Item-level cataloging
- Web-based instruction
- Writing or providing instructions for research guides (e.g., LibGuides)
- Group Research Instruction (e.g. the goal of this instruction is how to conduct research in a given field or for a specific type of project)
- Group Tool-based Instruction (e.g. the goal of this instruction is how to use Tableau or R or other software)

- Individual Research Consultations (e.g. the goal of this consultation is how to conduct research in a given field or for a specific type of project)
- Individual Tool-based teaching sessions e.g. the goal of this session is how to use Tableau or R or other software)
- Other - Write In

7. When do patrons most often contact you in the research lifecycle? (select all that apply)

- Planning stage: brainstorming, pre-project research ideas, tools for data collection, discussion of analysis at project end
- Mid-project to get help in finding better resources
- Mid-project to get help using tools
- Mid-project for publication submission help
- Post-project publication help
- Post-project metadata clean up
- Other - Write In

8. When instructing or consulting with a patron/researcher what types of resources do you typically recommend? (select all that apply)

- Abstracting and Indexing Databases
- Aggregator products (e.g. JSTOR, EBSCO)
- Google Scholar
- Relevant pieces of scholarship or specific scholars
- Discovery layer keyword searches
- Discovery layer subject searches (e.g. LCSH, MeSH)
- Catalog subject searches (e.g. LCSH, MeSH)
- Bibliographic management tools
- Other - Write In

HOW DO YOU INTERACT WITH METADATA

9. What are common questions do you receive from patrons/researchers about metadata?

10. If a patron/researcher approaches you about a specific research object in your collection, what are the most critical things you need to know about it before you can help the patron/researcher decide how to use it for their project? (select all that apply)

- Type of research object (monograph, article, dataset, etc.)
- Format
- Date published
- Authority of author or authors
- Authority of publishing body
- Use restrictions
- Reproduction restrictions
- Interlibrary loan options
- Other - Write In

METADATA SPECIFICS

11. What do you consider to be the most important pieces of metadata for your patrons when they ask for help with a search? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Fields List” on page 7

12. What pieces of information do you typically discuss in the context of consultation or instruction with younger or less

experienced researchers? (select all that apply)

Refer to the "Metadata Fields List" on page 7

13. What pieces of information do you typically discuss in the context of consultation or instruction with more advanced or expert researchers? (select all that apply)

Refer to the "Metadata Fields List" on page 7

14. When you talk to patrons/researchers about metadata, what types of standards or schema do you explain or teach? (select all that apply)

Refer to the "Standards or Schema List" on page 7

FOLLOW UP

15. We would like to carry out optional, follow-up interviews with some respondents only to clarify responses. Are you interested in participating?

- Yes
- No

Publisher Survey

INTRODUCTION

We are interested in what you know about metadata in your role at your company, how metadata is generated to describe research objects, and how you and your company use metadata in your workflows.

What do we mean by “metadata”?

Examples of common metadata required for published articles are bibliographic components, including authors, title, publication date, journal name, volume, pages, subjects, keywords, and digital object identifiers (DOI). Publishers often also ask authors/researchers to provide keywords to describe their articles.

What do we mean by “your end users”?

End users may be researchers, librarians, or others that use metadata to find and retrieve published resources of potential interest. They may also be service providers (e.g. Crossref, ORCID, CHORUS or library platforms) that disseminate this metadata through their systems.

In thinking about these things, please tell us a bit about yourself and consider the questions below:

TELL US ABOUT YOU

2. What is your job title or professional role?

TELL US ABOUT THOSE YOU WORK WITH

3. How does your publishing company currently support metadata education for your end users?

4. What would you like to see changed in how your company handles education for end users with respect to the metadata they enter and the metadata that is created in the processes of publication?

5. To the best of your knowledge, how is data entered into your system? We enter data in these ways: (select all that apply)

- Manually by content experts who work within your organization
- Manually by content experts who work outside of your organization
- Manually by the researchers depositing the content
- Automatically by workflows facilitated by external organizations like ORCID or Crossref
- Automatically by internally used software
- Other - Write In

6. What are the most critical issues for those who submit metadata to your publications? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Critical Challenges w/Metadata List” on page 7

7. What control do authors/researchers have over the metadata

associated with their publications after they have submitted them? (select one)

- No update capabilities
- Some control with certain fields
- All fields can be edited
- Other - Write In

HOW DO YOU INTERACT WITH METADATA

8. Where does your metadata go when it is exported to other systems? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Systems Using Metadata List” on page 7

9. Where are the critical issues in your workflows with respect to metadata required for inclusion in your publications? (select up to 5)

Refer to the “Critical Issues in Workflow List” on page 7

10. What are your methods to check the quality of the metadata in your system? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Quality Methods List” on page 7

METADATA SPECIFICS

11. What do you consider to be the most important pieces of metadata in indexing services? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Fields List” on page 7

12. What pieces of metadata does your system require for internal publishing tools? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Fields List” on page 7

13. What pieces of metadata does your system require for your online publishing platform? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Fields List” on page 7

14. Which standardized metadata schema do you use to describe your published items when you publish them or post them online? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Standards or Schema List” on page 7

FOLLOW UP

15. We would like to carry out optional, follow-up interviews with some respondents only to clarify responses. Are you interested in participating?

- Yes
- No

Repository Manager Survey

INTRODUCTION

We are interested in how you work with metadata in general, how you may generate metadata in describing research objects, and how your users may use metadata generated by your system.

What do we mean by “metadata”?

Examples of common metadata for research datasets are bibliographic components, including authors, title, publication date, journal name, volume, and pages that describe how the data were generated. Metadata may also include author-generated “data dictionaries” and other descriptors to facilitate the ability to find, retrieve and use datasets of potential interest. Publishers and resource stewards may also provide unique identifiers, like a digital object identifier (DOI) or a URL for a repository for Github or Open Science Framework, to aid in resource findability and access.

In thinking about what your repository (or others with which you are familiar) requires for deposition, access and discovery, please tell us a bit about yourself and consider the questions below:

TELL US ABOUT YOU

2. What is your job title or professional role in your organization?

3. What research areas does your repository serve?

4. What types of research objects does your repository store? (select all that apply)

- Journal articles
- Monographs
- Research Reports
- Conference Proceedings
- Datasets
- Code
- Other - Write In

TELL US ABOUT THOSE YOU WORK WITH

5. What are some common questions do you receive from researchers about your repository?

6. How well is your organization serving the intended communities, and what are pressing challenges to be addressed?

7. To the best of your knowledge, how is data entered into your system? We enter data in these ways: (select all that apply)

- Manually by content experts who work within your organization

- Manually by content experts who work outside of your organization
- Manually by the researchers depositing the content
- Automatically by workflows facilitated by external organizations like ORCID or Crossref
- Automatically by internally used software
- Other - Write In

8. What are the most critical issues for those who submit metadata to your repository? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Critical Challenges w/Metadata List” on page 7

HOW DO YOU INTERACT WITH METADATA

9. Where does your metadata go when it is exported to other systems? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Systems Using Metadata List” on page 7

10. Which is true for in the research objects that can be deposited in your repository? (select all that apply)

- Repository-required metadata is presented at time of deposit
- Content is deposit-ready with respect to format(s) and/or directory organization
- Content can be made deposit-ready by owner or others easily
- Content may not duplicate previously deposited research object
- Other - Write In

11. Where are the critical issues in your workflows with respect to metadata required for inclusion in your repository? (select up to 5)

Refer to the “Critical Issues in Workflow List” on page 7

12. What are your methods to check the quality of the metadata in your system? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Quality Methods List” on page 7

METADATA SPECIFICS

13. What pieces of information does your repository require for deposition? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Fields List” on page 7

14. What do you consider to be the most important pieces of metadata? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Fields List” on page 7

15. What metadata standard do you use for including objects in your repository? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Standards or Schema List” on page 7

FOLLOW UP

16. We would like to carry out optional, follow-up interviews with some respondents only to clarify responses. Are you interested in participating?

- Yes
- No

Researcher Survey

INTRODUCTION

We are interested in what you know about metadata; whether and how you generate metadata yourself; and whether and how you use metadata to find, assess, and use research objects.

What do we mean by “metadata”?

Metadata for research outputs commonly includes author details and other bibliographic information like title, publication date, pages, subjects, keywords, and digital object identifiers (DOIs). Indexing this information helps make these outputs more easily discoverable, for example, in abstracting and indexing databases and in content platforms like those provided by JSTOR, ProQuest, EBSCO, and Elsevier. In your work as a researcher, you may also be creating metadata about your work (for example, during manuscript submission), and using metadata to promote it. Please tell us a bit about yourself and answer the questions below as they pertain to how you conduct and publish your research.

TELL US ABOUT YOU

2. What is your research field and/or topic?

3. How long have you been working in this field?

- Less than 5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-20 years
- 20-30 years
- More than 30 years

4. Do you publish your research?

- Yes
- No

5. Do you collaborate with other researchers?

- Yes
- No

HOW DO YOU INTERACT WITH METADATA

6. When you think of the term “metadata” what comes to mind?

7. Does your research work include using research data management software?

- Yes
- No

METADATA SPECIFICS

8. What do you consider to be the most important pieces of information about research objects in order to make them accessible and useful to others in your field in future? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Fields List” on page 7

9. If you’re trying to find a good research object (e.g., an article

or dataset), what pieces of information are most helpful in finding what you seek? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Metadata Fields List” on page 7

10. What are the top five pieces of information you look at to help you decide if you should read/download a paper or book chapter?

Refer to the “Metadata Fields List” on page 7

11. If you’re trying to decide whether or not to read an article or a book chapter when you see an interesting title or scan through a table of contents what are the most important things for you to know about it before you read it in detail? (select all that apply)

- Whether I can access full text
- Online format
- Print format
- Date published
- Authority of author or authors
- Authority of publishing body
- Use restrictions (e.g. open access)
- Reproduction restrictions
- Details about the study population or study design
- Other - Write In

12. If you are trying to understand a data set, pieces of evidence or other scholarly artifacts you found or were sent to you by a colleague, what are the most critical things for you to know to evaluate credibility and usefulness before you can use it/ them? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Dataset Traits List” on page 7

13. What traits usually prevent you from using a dataset or piece of evidence? (select all that apply)

Refer to the “Dataset Traits List” on page 7

14. Where do you store or deposit your data sets, pieces of evidence, or other scholarly artifacts after you have finished with them? (select all that apply)

- Personal computer
- Personal cloud storage
- Institutional storage (e.g. institutional repository or cloud service)
- Public data repository or website
- Private data repository or website
- Online Content Management System
- Other - Write In

15. Which standardized metadata schema do you use to describe your research outputs when you publish them or post them online?

Refer to the “Standards or Schema List” on page 7

FOLLOW UP

16. We would like to carry out optional, follow-up interviews with some respondents only to clarify responses. Are you interested in participating?

- Yes
- No

Common Answer Lists

METADATA FIELDS LIST

- Title
- ISSN
- ISBN or other title identifier
- Author name(s)
- Author(s) affiliations
- Author ORCID(s)
- Year and Date of publication
- Volume (and Issue if relevant)
- Record type
- Page numbers
- Elocation ID
- Abstract
- Language of content
- Format of data (file types)
- Size of content files
- Usage restrictions (E.G. Copyright Statements, Permission for Use)
- Associated publications
- Associated data sets
- Funder ID(s)
- Funder Name(s)
- Grant ID(s)
- DOI
- non-DOI article identifiers (e.g. arXiv, PMID, UUID)
- LCSH Subjects
- MeSH Subjects
- Local controlled subject vocabulary
- Researcher/Author generated keywords
- Other - Write In
- None of the above

STANDARDS OR SCHEMA LIST

- Dublin Core
- EAD
- JATS
- MARC 21
- MEI
- METS
- MODS
- ONIX
- RDF
- TEI
- DataCite XML
- Bibframe
- KBART
- MARC XML
- UNIMARC
- Other - Write In
- None of the above
- Don't know

DATASET TRAITS LIST

- File formats
- Title of the data collection
- Size of dataset or pieces of evidence (not the number of subjects, but the size of the files in the collection)
- Length (e.g. of a film or musical recording or audio recording)
- Image capture information (e.g. photographic materials)
- Size of the sample set (number of subjects)
- Scope of the sample set
- Limitations of scope of the research
- Description about the data collection process or the creation of the material
- Description about how it is being used in research
- Date of collection or creation

- Usage restrictions like copyrights or data use agreements
- Financial costs
- Other - Write In

SYSTEMS USING METADATA LIST

- Crossref
- ORCID
- CHORUS
- DataCite
- PubMed
- PIVOT
- Aggregators like ProQuest, EBSCO, JSTOR
- Library Service Platforms like ExLibris, Ebsco Discovery, World Cat Discovery
- Libraries
- Other - Write In

CRITICAL CHALLENGES W/METADATA LIST

- Lack of basic knowledge of the term "metadata"
- Lack of knowledge of specific types of "metadata"
- Lack of understanding how the information they submit is transformed in your system
- Lack of understanding how your organization uses their information
- Time needed to add required information into data fields
- Problems gathering all the needed information for each data field
- Lack of knowledge about how end users will benefit from this metadata
- Lack of knowledge about the impact the metadata will have in discovery
- Frustrations with manual data entry for different types of research objects
- Other - Write In

CRITICAL ISSUES IN WORKFLOW LIST

- With the researcher
- With internally created metadata
- With externally created metadata
- With data clean up internally
- With data clean up externally (e.g. work done by outsourcers to enhance records)
- With points of deposition (e.g. adding metadata to the repository)
- With points of dissemination (e.g. sending your repository data to other organizations or individuals)
- With lack of controlled vocabulary for data entry
- Other - Write In

METADATA QUALITY METHODS LIST

- Automated validation rules
- Manual checking other internal systems
- Manual checking other external systems
- People/staff/content experts offering curation support for deposits
- Not applicable, no check for metadata quality is done at present
- Other - Write In